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Managing School-Community Relations For Quality Education In Public Secondary Schools In Delta State

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ABSTRACT

This study investigated the management of school-community relations as a determinant of quality education in public secondary schools in Delta State, Nigeria. The primary objective include examining the impact of effective management of school-community relations on educational quality, evaluating the current strategies employed by public secondary schools to manage relationships with their communities, and determining the extent of involvement of parents, local leaders. The study was guided by four research questions and four hypotheses amongst which was to ascertain how effective management of school-community relations enhance the quality of education in public secondary schools. The theoretical framework adopted was the social systems theory. The design for the study is ex-post facto. The population was four hundred and ninety five (495) schools made up of principals, management staff and teachers from public secondary schools in twenty five (25) Local Government Areas, based on the 2023/2024 academic calendar of the Ministry of Basic and Secondary Education. The sample size of 380 was derived from the Cochran Formula mathematical equation while random sampling technique was used to obtain the respondents. A self-structured questionnaire entitled ‘Questionnaire on managing school-community relations for quality education in public secondary schools in Delta State, (MSCRFQE) was used to obtain the needed responses. The findings reveal that effective management of school-community relations significantly enhances the quality of education. However, the current strategies for managing these relationships are found to be insufficient, indicating the need for improvement. The study also shows that parents, local leaders, and community organizations are involved to an average extent in the administration of public secondary schools. Furthermore, school-community collaboration is shown to positively influence student performance and the condition of school facilities. It was recommended that developing structured frameworks for community engagement, training school leaders in communication and relationship management, as well as redesigning community involvement strategies to be more inclusive.

Keywords: Managing, School-Community, Relations, Quality Education, Secondary schools.

INTRODUCTION

Education as the foundation for personal and societal development has globally been accepted as the colloquium that generates the necessary prerequisite for the acquisition of skill and expertise, leading to individual and collective advancement, achieved within the confines of a well-organized environment, often referred to as an academic community. This community however, does not exists in isolation, as it is a function of numerous other miniature communities thriving within it as a derivative of the much larger environment within which the academic community exists (Nkedishu, Ekwevugbe & Akpoguma, 2025)

Quality education refers to an inclusive and holistic process that ensures learners acquire not only foundational knowledge and skills but also critical thinking abilities, emotional intelligence, and the capacity to participate meaningfully in society. According to Papanthymou and Darra (2023) quality in education is associated with the improvement of the learning process, and the improvement results from the implementation of appropriate teaching practices and methods, such as the design of a curriculum in order to meet students' learning needs thereby improving the services provided by school (Dritsa, 2016; Imonivwerha, Ekwevugbe & Okandeji, 2011)

School community according to Hameed & Al-Salam (2024) is an abstraction of the school cited with the local community. This is a "place-based" approach that emphasizes on the school in relation to its external community as a provider of a range of services and is considered as a supporter of development, as these schools combine different scenarios or features, to suit the diverse needs of learners that emanates from these local communities, with each system adopting different school models tailored to suit its own requirements, learners' abilities, challenges, culture, regional aspirations, and their interrelationships with the external community or society. This dynamic interaction underscores the importance of understanding how schools function as microcosms of the larger society and how they contribute to the social fabric by nurturing future generations (Etor, 2011; Elkins & Forrester, 2010 ; Beltran, 2009)),

The school therefore as an academic organization, is sited within a broader community, saddled with the primary purpose of fulfilling social functions (Nishimura, 2017; Jacobson, 2016). When families, local organizations, and community leaders actively engage with schools, they help bridge the gap between home and school, reinforcing the importance of education and creating a sense of shared responsibility for students' academic and social development. This community-school dynamics has been shown to enhance student outcomes, not only academically but also in terms of personal growth and resilience (Obasi, 2022; Ekwevugbe & Efebor, 2025). Additionally, strong community ties can reduce barriers to education, such as financial constraints or social isolation, by offering resources, mentorship, and opportunities that might otherwise be unavailable. Consequently, this interconnectedness between schools and communities can be a catalyst for upward mobility, allowing individuals to break free from cycles of poverty and disadvantage as cordial relationship between the school and community is therefore a pre-requisite for achieving meaningful quality educational objective (Gital, 2019 ; Ekwevugbe, 2014).

Strategies for managing school-community relations refer to the planned and systematic approaches employed by school leaders to foster effective collaboration, communication, and partnership between the school and its surrounding community. These strategies are designed to enhance mutual understanding, promote stakeholder involvement, and support educational and developmental goals through inclusive decision-making, cultural responsiveness, community engagement, and continuous evaluation (Epstein, 2011).

The models of School-Community Relationships that exists between schools and communities can be conceptualized through various paradigms that illustrate the dynamics of interaction, engagement, and collaboration. Two such models—alienative relationships and cooperative relationships offer distinct perspectives on the nature of these interactions, highlighting the degree of involvement, trust, and mutual benefit between schools and the communities they serve.

According to Duru-Uremadu, (2017) alienative relationship refers to when there is virtually no exchange of resources or ideas between the school and the community, and as a result the school restricts its activities to its traditional role of teaching and learning and the improvement of the instructional process . In contrast to the alienative model, a cooperative relationship is defined by mutual respect, collaboration, and shared responsibility between schools and communities. This model reflects an integrated approach to education, wherein schools and community members actively work together to support students' academic, social, and emotional development (Igwebuike, Okandeji & Ekwevugbe, 2013). According to, Ibiam (2011), this type of school community relationship is based on the premise that the school and the community have something to offer and benefit from each other. A cooperative relationship fosters an environment in which both parties view each other as partners in the educational setting.

Management of school-community relations refers to the strategic and systematic process through which school leaders and administrators plan, implement, coordinate, and evaluate interactions and partnerships between the school and its surrounding community. This involves fostering effective communication, building mutual trust, engaging diverse stakeholders, and aligning school goals with community values and needs to enhance educational outcomes and social cohesion (Epstein, 2011). This approach to management encompasses managerial functions—such as planning, organizing, leading, and controlling—applied specifically to the development of collaborative initiatives, resource sharing, participatory governance, and community involvement in school affairs. Effective management in this context ensures that schools are responsive to the cultural, economic, and social dynamics of the communities they serve, thereby contributing to a supportive and inclusive educational environment.

At the core of managing school-community relations is the development of trust, mutual respect, and shared responsibility. Educational administrators must employ managerial functions of planning, organizing, leading, and controlling to ensure that interactions between schools and community stakeholders are structured, goal-oriented, and sustainable. This includes creating mechanisms for regular communication, involving parents and community members in decision-making processes, and establishing partnerships with local organizations, businesses, and governmental agencies (Agadagba & Ekwevugbe, 2025).

The study adopted the Social Systems Theory which views the school as an open system interacting with its environment.

Statement of the Problem

The management of school-community relations is a crucial determinant of the quality of education in public secondary schools. While schools are expected to work collaboratively with their surrounding communities to foster educational excellence, significant challenges persist in managing these relationships effectively. The disconnect that exists between the school and its community, impedes the optimal development of both school and community. The schools, made up of students, teachers, administrators, and school staff, focuses on day-to-day academic and administrative activities, which is exclusive to the school's external community leading to a lack of alignment with the broader expectations of the community.

The external community, consisting of parents, local businesses, government bodies, and other stakeholders, are disengaged from immediate academic activities lacks the resources, competence and commitment to support the school in meaningful ways leading to communication gap, limited involvement, and misaligned priorities (Abraham & Ememe 2012) While the external community perceives the school as not effectively involving them in decision-making processes and failure to engage in a mutually beneficial partnership.

This study therefore seeks to explore the intricacies of managing school-community relations in public secondary schools in Delta State, focusing particularly on the complex dynamics between the internal and external communities.

Research Questions

1. How can effective management of school-community relations enhance the quality of education in public secondary schools in Delta State, Nigeria?
2. What are the current strategies used by public secondary schools in Delta State to manage relationships with their communities?
3. To what extent are parents, local leaders, and community organizations involved in the administration of public secondary schools for quality education?
4. How does school-community collaboration influence student performance, school facilities, and teaching quality?

Research Hypotheses

The following research hypotheses were raised to further direct the study;

Ho1: There is no significant relationship between effective management of school-community relations and enhanced quality of education in public secondary schools in Delta State

Ho2: There is no significant relationship between current strategies used by public secondary schools and the management of relationships with their communities in Delta State

Ho3: There is no significant relationship between involvement of parents, local leaders, and community organizations in the administration of public secondary schools for quality education

Ho4: There is no significant relationship between school-community collaboration influence and student performance for quality education in secondary school

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

The design for this study is the ex-post facto research design. It studied the intricacies of managing school-community relations for quality education in public secondary schools in Delta State.

Population of the Study

The population adopted in this study is from the four hundred and ninety five (495) schools made up of principals, management staff and teachers from public secondary schools in twenty five (25) Local Government Areas in Delta State, Nigeria, based on the 2023/2024 academic calendar of the Ministry of Basic and Secondary Education, Delta State.

Sample and Sampling Technique

The number of respondents used for the study was 380 derived from the Cochran Formula mathematical equation. The study adopted the random sampling technique to select one (1) principal, 1 Management Staff, and three (3) teachers making the total of (5) respondents respectively per school sampled.

Instrument for Data Collection

The instrument used in this study is a self-made questionnaire entitled 'Questionnaire on managing school-community relations for quality education in public secondary schools in Delta State, (MSCRFQE).

To ensure face and content validity of the research instrument, a copy of the drafted questionnaire was sent to experts for vetting, corrections and modifications.

Test-retest was used to ensure the reliability of the questionnaire. The completed questionnaire was analyzed using Pearson's product correlation coefficient, the resultant value of 0.79 was adjudged reliable for the study.

RESULTS

Research Question One: *How can effective management of school-community relations enhance the quality of education in public secondary schools in Delta State, Nigeria?*

Table 1. Mean score of the variables on how effective management of school-community relations enhance the quality of education in public secondary schools in Delta State, Nigeria

S/No	Teacher attendance scheduling	N	SA	A	D	SD	Mean
1	The school has a clear strategy for engaging the community	380	63	87	112	118	2.250
2	The school leadership regularly consults with community stakeholders	380	78	55	122	125	2.226
3	Community feedback is used to make school decisions	380	52	77	130	121	2.158
4	Conflicts between the school and community are handled constructively	380	112	128	80	60	2.768
5	The school organizes regular forums for parents and community members	380	90	109	95	86	2.534
6	Parents are actively involved in school activities	380	47	87	110	136	2.118
7	The community contributes resources to support the school	380	108	112	70	90	2.626
8	There is mutual trust between the school and the community.	380	113	127	80	60	2.771
9	The school communicates openly and frequently with the community	380	106	116	79	79	2.655
10	Local organizations participate in school improvement programs	380	108	120	85	67	2.708
11	School attendance rates have improved due to community support	380	111	124	67	78	2.705
12	Teacher motivation and commitment have increased due to community support	380	101	136	54	89	2.655
13	Community involvement has led to better discipline among students.	380	117	127	49	87	2.721
14	The physical infrastructure of the school has improved due to NGO and community support	380	121	132	85	42	2.761
15	Students' academic performance has improved in recent years due to community support	380	98	141	69	72	2.697
Total Mean							2.557

Key: 0.1-1.25 = Strongly Disagree, 1.26 – 2.4 = Disagree, 2.5 – 3.75 = Agree, 3.76 – 4.00 = Strongly Agree

The table 1 displays all variable items regarding how can effective management of school-community relations enhance the quality of education in public secondary schools in Delta State, Nigeria having mean scores of 2.557 that is above the average mean mark of 2.50, and falling within the 2.5 – 3.75 = Agree category. Indicating therefore that respondent's agree that effective management of school-community relations enhance the quality of education in public secondary schools in Delta State. However they disagree that the school has a clear strategy for engaging the community, that the school leadership regularly consults with community stakeholders, Community feedback are used to make school decisions, and that Parents are actively involved in school activities based on the fact that the mean score for these variable items mentioned were below the 2.50 mean benchmark. Thus, based on the overall mean score it can be concluded that effective management of school-community relations enhance the quality of education in public secondary schools in Delta State.

Research Question Two: *What are the current strategies used by public secondary schools in Delta State to manage relationships with their communities?*

Table 2. Mean score of the variables on the current strategies used by public secondary schools in Delta State to manage relationships with their communities

S/No	Teacher attendance scheduling	N	SA	A	SD	D	Mean
1	The school organizes regular Parent-Teacher Association (PTA) meetings to engage parents	380	122	114	80	64	2.774
2	The school always communicates with community stakeholders through newsletters, SMS, or local media.	380	60	53	130	137	2.095
3	School leaders invite community members to participate in decision-making processes	380	40	63	121	156	1.966
4	School leaders invite community members to participate in curriculum structuring processes.	380	32	50	130	168	1.858
5	There is a designated committee or liaison officer responsible for school-community relations.	380	109	86	95	90	2.563
6	The school conducts community outreach programs (e.g., health talks, clean-up campaigns)	380	120	140	74	46	2.879
7	The school collects feedback from parents and community members through surveys or suggestion boxes.	380	114	130	78	58	2.789
8	Community representatives are involved in school project planning and monitoring.	380	70	90	111	109	2.318
9	School administrators maintain an open-door policy for parents and community leaders.	380	57	89	104	130	2.192
10	The school holds cultural, sports, or social events that involve the local community	380	116	131	49	84	2.734
11	Organizing community engagement strategies in order to build effective relationships.	380	120	135	57	68	2.808
12	The school receives active support from the community	380	132	149	46	53	2.947
13	Teachers and staff actively involve the community in daily decision making	380	49	86	130	115	2.182
14	The school leadership regularly reviews and updates its community engagement strategies.	380	86	43	120	131	2.221
15	The school works with community leaders to resolve school-related challenges	380	99	156	60	65	2.761
Total Mean							2.444

Key: 0.1-1.25 = Strongly Disagree, 1.26 – 2.4 = Disagree, 2.5 – 3.75 = Agree, 3.76 – 4.00 = Strongly Agree

The table 2 highlights variable items regarding the current strategies used by public secondary schools in Delta State to manage relationships with their communities having mean scores 2.444 that are below the 2.50 mean bench mark, and also falling within the 1.26 – 2.4 = Disagree mean category. This indicates that not all of the variables mentioned were implemented or used by public secondary schools in Delta State. It can therefore be concluded that among the current strategies used by public secondary schools in Delta State to manage relationships with their communities were organizing regular Parent-Teacher Association (PTA) meetings to engage parents, having a designated committee or liaison officer responsible for school-community relations. conducting community outreach programs such as health

talks and clean-up campaigns, collecting feedback from parents and community members through surveys or suggestion boxes, holding cultural, sports, or social events that involve the local community, Organizing community engagement strategies in order to build effective relationship, receiving active support from the community and working with community leaders to resolve school-related challenges. These were the current strategies used by public secondary schools in Delta State to manage relationships with their communities.

Research Question Three: *To what extent are parents, local leaders, and community organizations involved in the administration of public secondary schools for quality education?*

Table 3. Mean score of how the extent to which are parents, local leaders, and community organizations involved in the administration of public secondary schools for quality education

S/No	Teacher attendance scheduling	N	VLE	AE	LE	NE	Mean
1	Parents are actively involved in Parent-Teacher Association (PTA) meeting	380	124	122	72	62	2.811
2	Parents participate in making key decisions affecting the school	380	150	66	88	76	2.763
3	Parents are regularly informed about school policies and developments	380	141	100	65	74	2.811
4	Parents contribute to planning school improvement initiatives	380	160	87	68	65	2.900
5	Parent feedback is considered in the administration of the school	380	124	78	120	58	2.705
6	Traditional rulers or community leaders are consulted on school issues	380	44	69	131	136	2.055
7	Local leaders are invited to school meetings or events involving planning and review.	380	164	88	55	73	2.903
8	Community leaders help in resolving conflicts within the school system	380	33	75	119	153	1.968
9	School administrators collaborate with local leaders to promote discipline and moral standards.	380	164	98	62	56	2.879
10	Religious or social groups contribute to the school's administration or oversight.	380	51	77	108	144	2.092
11	Community organizations are represented on school boards or committees.	380	36	59	111	174	1.887
12	Community-based organizations (CBOs) or NGOs partner with the school in development projects	380	147	133	40	60	2.966
13	Local businesses support school operations through donations or services.	380	136	101	73	70	2.797
14	The school collaborates with community organizations to improve academic outcomes	380	160	114	45	61	2.982
15	The involvement of community stakeholders has improved student performance.	380	192	91	57	40	3.145
Total Mean							2.644

Key: 0.1-1.25 = No Extent, 1.26 – 2.4 = Low Extent, 2.5 – 3.75 = Average Extent, 3.76 – 4.00 = Very Large Extent

The table 3 showcases all variable items regarding the extent to which parents, local leaders, and community organizations are involved in the administration of public secondary schools for quality education with the overall mean score of 2.644 above the 2.50 mean bench mark, and also within the category of 2.5 – 3.75 = Average Extent. However, the result also showed that Community leaders do not help in resolving conflicts within the school system, Religious or social groups do not contribute to the school’s administration or oversight and Community organizations are not represented on school boards or committees, this is as a result of the fact that their individual mean scores were below the average mean benchmark of 2.50, thereby implying that to an average extent, parents, local leaders, and community organizations are involved in the administration of public secondary schools for quality education in Delta State.

Research Question Four: How does school-community collaboration influence student performance, school facilities, and teaching quality?

Table 4. Mean score of how school-community collaboration influence student performance, school facilities, and teaching quality

S/No	Teacher attendance scheduling	N	SA	A	SD	D	Mean
1	Parents and community leaders participate in school maintenance and development projects	380	26	54	140	160	1.858
2	Collaboration with community stakeholders helps in addressing student behavioral issues.	380	132	88	116	44	2.811
3	School-community collaboration has improved students’ academic performance	380	130	120	70	60	2.842
4	Students perform better when parents are actively involved in school activities	380	162	68	84	66	2.858
5	Mentorship or support from community members contributes to student success.	380	162	108	45	65	2.966
6	Community-based programs (e.g., tutoring, motivational talks) help students stay focused	380	174	90	71	45	3.034
7	Community contributions have led to improved school buildings and infrastructure	380	124	144	42	70	2.847
8	Local organizations and individuals donate resources (e.g., books, furniture) to the school.	380	188	93	38	61	3.074
9	Collaborative efforts have resulted in better-equipped classrooms and learning environments.	380	186	94	42	58	3.074
10	Community and NGOs support helps the school address urgent facility-related needs.	380	170	112	51	47	3.066
11	Support from the community motivates teachers to perform better	380	106	133	66	75	2.711
12	Community involvement leads to increased accountability in teaching practices	380	152	118	50	60	2.953
13	Collaboration helps attract and retain qualified teachers in the school	380	121	155	47	57	2.895
14	Teachers benefit from community-organized workshops, training, or support programs.	380	178	113	35	54	3.092
15	Community feedback is used to evaluate and improve teaching effectiveness.	380	199	125	22	34	3.287
Total Mean							2.891

Key: 0.1-1.25 = Strongly Disagree, 1.26 – 2.4 = Disagree, 2.5 – 3.75 = Agree, 3.76 – 4.00 = Strongly Agree

The table 4 showcases all variable items regarding how school-community collaboration influence student performance, school facilities, and teaching quality with each item having a mean score above the 2.50 mean bench mark, except for variable items 8, stating that Parents and community leaders do not participate in school maintenance and development projects based on its mean score of 1.858 that is below the 2.50 average mean benchmark. Thus it can be concluded based on the general mean score of 2.891 that is above the average mean benchmark of 2.50 and also falling within the category of 2.5 – 3.75 = Agree, implying that the respondents agree that the above variables raised were how school-community collaboration influence student performance, school facilities, and teaching quality in secondary schools in Delta State.

Research Hypotheses

Hypothesis One:

Ho1: There is no significant relationship between effective management of school-community relations and enhanced quality of education in public secondary schools in Delta State

Table 5 One t-test table on significant relationship between effective management of school-community relations and enhanced quality of education in public secondary schools in Delta State

Variables	N	Mean	SD	t-calc	t-crit	Df	P	Decision
effective management of school-community relations	9	2.456	0.252	2.407	1.761	14	0.0316	Reject Null
enhanced quality of education in public secondary schools	6	2.708	0.031					

Table 5 show a t –test measuring the frequency and mean values for the variables between effective management of school-community relations and enhanced quality of education in public secondary schools in Delta State. The table revealed an absolute t-calculated value of 2.407 exceeding the standard t-critical or table value of 1.761, with a p value of 0.0316, therefore rejecting the null hypothesis indicating therefore that there is a significant relationship between the effective management of school-community relations and enhanced quality of education in public secondary schools in Delta State.

Hypothesis Two:

Ho2: There is no significant relationship between current strategies used by public secondary schools and the management of relationships with their communities in Delta State

Table 6 One sample t test table on significant relationship between current strategies used by public secondary schools and the management of relationships with their communities in Delta State

Variables	N	Mean	SD	t-calc	t-crit	df	P	Decision
current strategies used by public secondary schools	7	2.418	0.400	0.564	1.761	14	0.582	Accept Null
the management of relationships with their school communities	8	2.520	0.300					

Table 6 show a t–test measuring the frequency and mean values for the variables between current strategies used by public secondary schools and the management of relationships with their communities in Delta State. The table revealed an absolute t-calculated value of 0.564 less than the standard t-critical

or table value of 1.761, with a p value of 0.582, therefore accepting the null hypothesis indicating therefore that there is not significant relationship between current strategies being adopted by public secondary schools and the management of relationships with their communities in Delta State.

.Hypothesis Three:

Ho3: There is no significant relationship between involvement of parents, local leaders, and community organizations in the administration of public secondary schools for quality education

Table 7 t-test table on significant relationship between involvement of parents, local leaders, and community organizations in the administration of public secondary schools for quality education

Variables	N	Mean	SD	t-calc	t-crit	Df	P	Decision
involvement of parents, local leaders	11	2.525	0.403	2.141	1.761	14	0.052	Reject Null
community organizations in the administration of public secondary schools for quality education	4	2.973	0.123					

Table 7 show a t –test measuring the frequency and mean values for the variables between involvement of parents, local leaders, and community organizations in the administration of public secondary schools for quality education. The table revealed an absolute t-calculated value of 2.141 exceeding the standard t-critical or table value of 1.761, with a p value of 0.052, therefore rejecting the null hypothesis indicating therefore that there is a significant relationship between involvement of parents, local leaders, and community organizations in the administration of public secondary schools for quality education.

Hypothesis Four:

Ho4: There is no significant relationship between school-community collaboration influence and student performance for quality education in secondary school

Table 8 t-test table on significant relationship between school-community collaboration influence and student performance for quality education in secondary school

Variables	N	Mean	SD	t-calc	t-crit	Df	P	Decision
school-community collaboration influence	2	2.335	0.477	4.432	1.761	14	0.001	Reject Null
student performance for quality education in secondary school	13	2.977	0.143					

Table 8 show a t –test measuring the frequency and mean values for the variables between school-community collaboration influence and student performance for quality education in secondary school. The table revealed an absolute t-calculated value of 4.432 exceeding the standard t-critical or table value of 1.761, with a p value of 0.001, thereby rejecting the null hypotheses and accepting the alternate hypothesis stating that there is a significant relationship between school-community collaboration influence and student performance for quality education in secondary school.

DISCUSSION OF RESULT

The study revealed that effective management of school-community relations enhance the quality of education in public secondary schools in Delta State. Obassi (2022) concurs stating that the relationship

that exists between the school and the community is a mutual with reciprocal benefits, as the school affects and is affected by the community, implying that, they are both independent of each other, as no society can function healthily without the school and no school can succeed without the help of the community. However it was revealed that the school does not have a clear strategy for engaging the community, school leadership does not regularly consults with community stakeholders, Community feedback are not used to make school decisions, and parents are not actively involved in school activities. However, the study concludes that effective management of school-community relations enhances the quality of education in public secondary schools in Delta State.

The study also showed that among the current strategies used by public secondary schools in Delta State to manage relationships with their communities were organizing regular Parent-Teacher Association (PTA) meetings to engage parents, having a designated committee or liaison officer responsible for school-community relations. conducting community outreach programs such as health talks and clean-up campaigns, collecting feedback from parents and community members through surveys or suggestion boxes, holding cultural, sports, or social events that involve the local community, organizing community engagement strategies in order to build effective relationship, receiving active support from the community and working with community leaders to resolve school-related challenges. This is in consonance with the studies of Bhaskar & Lajwanti (2019) stating that It is strategy that is being used to manage, control and improve the process and products of education.

The study also showed that to an average extent, parents, local leaders, and community organizations are involved in the administration of public secondary schools for quality education in Delta State. This is done by provision of resources, manpower and funds to the schools in their areas (Koko & Nwiyi, 2006 ; Anho & Ekwevugbe, 2025).

Furthermore, the study showed that School-community collaboration has improved students' academic performance, Students perform better when parents are actively involved in school activities, Mentorship or support from community members contributes to student success, Community-based programs (e.g., tutoring, motivational talks) help students stay focused, Collaboration with community stakeholders helps in addressing student behavioral issues, Community contributions have led to improved school buildings and infrastructure, Local organizations and individuals donate resources (e.g., books, furniture) to the school, Parents and community leaders participate in school maintenance and development projects, Collaborative efforts have resulted in better-equipped classrooms and learning environments. Community and NGOs support helps the school address urgent facility-related needs, Support from the community motivates teachers to perform better, Community involvement leads to increased accountability in teaching practices, Collaboration helps attract and retain qualified teachers in the school, Teachers benefit from community-organized workshops, training, or support programs and Community feedback is used to evaluate and improve teaching effectiveness were areas where school-community collaboration influenced student performance, school facilities, and teaching quality in secondary schools in Delta State. This is consistent with Crawford (2020) stating that the idea of reciprocity is easily seen in how that parent in turn influences the child.

Conclusively, the study revealed that poor communication between school administrators and community stakeholders, Community members not regularly informed about school activities or needs, lack of platforms for regular dialogue between the school and the community, Language or cultural differences hinder effective engagement with some community members, Parents show little interest in participating in school governance or PTA activities, Community leaders are often unavailable or uninterested in school matters, lack of shared responsibility between the school and the community, Community members feel that their opinions are not valued by school authorities, Limited financial resources prevent active community involvement in school development, community members not in a financial position to support the school, school lacking funds to organize community engagement programs, school administrators not prioritizing community involvement in decision-making, no clear policy or framework guiding school-community collaboration, Leadership pattern in schools affecting continuity in building community relationships and Political interference from community leaders negatively affects school

administration were some of the major challenges faced in fostering effective school-community relationships in Delta State public secondary schools. This is in line with Adam & Landford (2021) following the organizational structure of open systems theory, acknowledging that the activities of participants who may have different intentions, but situated within their larger environments rely on processes of communication and feedback for continuous maintenance among interdependent subsystems. The study also showed that there is a significant relationship between the effective management of school-community relations and enhanced quality of education in public secondary schools in Delta State, as Mitrofanova (2011) and Bibire (2014) were of the opinion that schools and communities work with each other to meet their mutual goals of provision and management of education as well as teaching, learning and enforcement of processes. It was also highlighted by the results of the study that there is no significant relationship between current strategies being adopted by public secondary schools and the management of relationships with their communities in Delta State.

The study further revealed that there is a significant relationship between involvement of parents, local leaders, and community organizations in the administration of public secondary schools for quality education. The study added, that there is a significant relationship between school-community collaboration influence and student performance for quality education in secondary school (Ekwevugbe & Money, 2006). Summarily the study also showed that there is no significant relationship between challenges faced by school-community relationships and effective quality of education in public secondary schools in Delta State. This result is in concurrence with the Input-Output Theory of Education, which emphasizes internal school factors—such as teacher quality, student aptitude, and instructional methods—are described as key determinants of educational outcomes, rather than external factors or community relationships.

Findings

This study examined managing school-community relations for quality education in public secondary schools in Delta State, Nigeria. The finding from the study reveals:

1. that effective management of school-community relations enhance the quality of education in public secondary schools in Delta State.
2. that the current strategies used by public secondary schools in Delta State to manage relationships with their communities includes organizing regular PTA meetings, having a liaison committees amongst others.
3. that to an average extent, parents, local leaders, and community organizations are involved in the administration of public secondary schools for quality education in Delta State.
4. that school-community collaboration influence student performance, school facilities, and teaching quality when there is effective collaboration on all fronts.

CONCLUSION

The research concludes that there is a significant relationship between the effective management of school-community relations and enhanced quality of education in public secondary schools. Furthermore, there is no significant relationship between current strategies being adopted by public secondary schools and the management of relationships with their communities in Delta State. However there is a significant relationship between involvement of parents, local leaders, and community organizations in the administration of public secondary schools for quality education. This according to (Hallinger & Heck 1998; Evans & Johnson, 1990) refers to an effective principal management feature that is seen as a crucial component for academic success.

It was also discovered that there is a significant relationship between school-community collaboration influence and student performance for quality education in secondary school, as explained by Okam and Bozimo (2004), it is this collaboration and interlinking of a school with the host community that creates the difference.

RECOMMENDATIONS

The findings and conclusion of this study has led the researcher to make the following recommendations

1. Public secondary schools in Delta State should develop formalized frameworks for community engagement, involving parents, local leaders, and civil society organizations. These frameworks should include regular stakeholder meetings, collaborative school development plans, and shared decision-making processes.
2. School administrators should be trained in communication, conflict resolution, and stakeholder management to foster a more productive and innovative school environment that support teaching and learning excellence.
3. Boards of governors or school-based management committees should include active representation from parents and local community groups. Their participation in budgeting, monitoring, and policy-making can increase accountability and contribute directly to improvements in student outcomes.

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